

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF RABBIT BREEDING AND BREEDING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *Today, the rabbit breeding industry occupies one of the important places in the world economy and consumption. In particular, along with meat, milk, eggs and fish products, the production of rabbit meat is also important in animal husbandry. After all, rabbit breeding is one of the most profitable industries, and its meat, in particular, is considered nutritious. According to experts, the rabbit's meat and skin, as well as its oil, are environmentally friendly products that can be used in the preparation of various creams in cosmetology. In general, the further development of the rabbit breeding industry, the processing of its skin and fur in an industrial way, and its exportation is considered a great income for business entities and entrepreneurs. The following article talks about the techniques of raising and breeding rabbits.*

Keywords: *rabbits, sexual cycle, breeding schedule, intensive rabbit breeding, Polish breed, Flemish giant, vulva, temporary infertility, false pregnancy.*

INTRODUCTION

Rabbits have a high reproduction rate compared to other livestock. They become sexually mature within a few months of birth and have a relatively short gestation period. In rabbits, the sexual cycle repeats very quickly. With an intensive breeding program, we can expect 60 litters per year from one mother rabbit. Such intensive breeding is not recommended for beginners and is rarely used in commercial production.

When establishing a breeding system for rabbits, the first thing to consider is the purpose of raising rabbits. If you are raising rabbits for meat, you should focus on producing as many young rabbits as possible. If you are interested in the ornamental species of rabbits, you should pay attention to having several children every year and to the sexual maturity of the rabbits.

Literature analysis. During the analysis, it was found that the further development of the rabbit breeding network, the technique of raising and breeding rabbits is a source of great income, and it is one of the most important areas in the economy and animal husbandry.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Rabbit breeding schedules are usually based on 7-day intervals for ease of keeping records. Most commercial producers aim to breed rabbits 14 to 21 days after farrowing. A 35-day breeding schedule is recommended if you are new to rabbit farming. As you gain experience, you can shorten the interval between calving and breeding. Regardless of what breeding scheme you use, always check the condition of the rabbits before mating them. After 21 days of giving birth, it is not wise to mate a rabbit in poor condition again, as this may affect its reproductive capacity.

This can lead to low birth rates, small children, or high birth rates. To limit the risk of possible problems, make sure that the rabbit is in optimal health conditions. If possible, combine several in one day or several days. Calving occurs approximately at the same time (after 28-32

days), which makes it easier to raise children if necessary. Seven or eight litters should be expected, but depending on the particular breed of rabbit, there may be fewer or more from time to time.

Adult males can be used for a single mating for a long time every day without affecting their fertility. However, if they are used for multiple inseminations in a day or two, they should rest for a few days before mating again.

Large commercial hares may keep one male for every 10-15 rabbits, while small producers may need 1 to 5 or even 1 to 2 males. An intensive breeding program requires more males to provide the same amount of service than a less intensive breeding schedule. If you are trying to ensure proper breeding, you must remember to use the same male when breeding.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Different breeds of rabbits reach sexual maturity at different ages. Smaller breeds reach sexual maturity earlier than larger breeds. Small breeds (such as Polish) can be bred at 4-5 months of age. Medium breeds (such as New Zealand and California breeds) become sexually mature at 6-7 months of age. Giant breeds (such as the Flemish Giant) must be at least 7 months old when bred. Females of all rabbit breeds reach sexual maturity earlier than males. This means that it can be put into production before men of the same age.

When they tend to mate, they usually show signs of heat. They may act restlessly, rub their chins against food and water bowls or other equipment, and show a desire to join other rabbits. The vulva (female external genitalia) is slightly swollen, moist, and reddish, purple in color when the female is ready for fertilization. A small, dry, pale (white) vulva means that the female is not ready for reproduction. Also, if the female is in heat, she may lie on her stomach or raise her tail when touched. Before attempting any mating, check both of them to make sure they are in good condition and free of disease and injury.

Before mating, it is necessary to transfer the female to the male rabbit's cage. Because the female animal can try to protect herself when another rabbit is introduced into the cage. In addition, when a male rabbit is placed in a strange cage, it takes a long time for him to smell and learn the surroundings. When an active female ready to mate and an experienced male are placed, mating occurs almost immediately. Young, inexperienced rabbits may take longer to mate than experienced rabbits. When the mating act is over, the male rabbit usually lies back or on its side.

Some rabbit breeders allow the female to mate twice with the male before returning her to the cage. Others prefer to return the female to the same male for a second mating 8-12 hours after the first mating. Be sure to record all mating dates (eg, placing a home box in the female's cage) to prepare for the birth in time.

DISCUSSION

Often the female refuses to mate with the male rabbit. When this happens, try her with another male rabbit or return her to her cage and try her again in 2-4 days. Care should be taken to ensure that there are no unmated female rabbits in the male rabbit's cage. An aggressive male rabbit and a reluctant female rabbit left alone together can harm each other. In some cases, the female rabbit may need to be kept for mating. Hold the female by the shoulder with one hand. Place your other hand under his body between his hind legs (this will raise his rear to normal height for serving) and move his tail up or to one side. Most male rabbits easily adapt to such help from a rabbit breeder.

Rabbits often show a natural decline in productivity in late summer, fall, and early winter. At this time, it is necessary to select rabbits with good productivity and pay attention to their mating.

Exposure to temperatures above 85°F for 5 consecutive days may cause temporary infertility in male rabbits. Older male rabbits are more susceptible to heat than younger male rabbits and can become sterile for 60 to 90 days. To reduce male infertility due to hot weather, keep breeding male rabbits in the coolest part of the hares and mate them frequently.

False pregnancy is a condition in which a female appears to be pregnant but is not. This can occur as a result of sterile mating or physical stimulation, such as being imposed by another rabbit, which causes a physiological response similar to pregnancy in the female. During pseudopregnancy, which lasts about 17 days, the female does not give birth. She can build a nest, even if she is not pregnant. Although the condition is normal and not harmful to the female, it delays breeding.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it should be said that another common problem of the reproductive system is failure to conceive after mating. This is usually because they are overweight or haven't bred in a long time. Being overweight can also cause problems, as they tend to be lazy and lack libido (sexual desire). Poor physical condition, old age, disease, injury, and poor nutrition are other factors that cause reproductive problems. As a rabbit breeder, you should try to keep your breeding animals organized, active and healthy for the best reproductive performance.

REFERENCES

1. Javkharov O., Mominova F. Prospects for the organization of rabbit farming <https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/tibbiyot/article/view/4585/4126>.
2. Kushokov J. "Rabbit breeding" Tashkent. 1994.
3. Ibragimov B.B. and others. Recommendation on breeding, feeding and keeping rabbits in farms and private farms. Samarkand, 2020.
4. Abdurahmanova, M. (2021). LEGAL FUNDAMENTALS OF LAND RESOURCES OF USANCE TO ACHIEVE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY. Экономика и финансы (Узбекистан), (Спецвыпуск 4), 187-189.
5. Bokiyeвна, T. P., Akbarovna, S. M., Sharipovna, K. G., Xudjiyarovna, A. K., & Subhanovich, A. A. (2019). Formation of the communicative competence of students in the process of teaching a foreign language in a non-language university. Religación: Revista de Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades, 4(20), 218-221.
6. Iriskulov, A. T., Aslanov, A. S., & Subhonova, A. A. Q. (2021). Possible dangers for a language which affect to its global status. Scientific progress, 2(2), 168-174.
7. Mamatkadirovna, K. G. (2022). Innovative Educational Technologies in the Educational Process. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 15, 108-110.
8. Otajanova, M. O. (2016). NEW APPROACH TO THE TRADITIONS. Theoretical & Applied Science, (11), 8-12.
9. Shukrulloevich, T. J., & Subxanovich, A. A. (2022). SUGGESTIONS AIMED AT THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN.
10. Shukrulloevich, T. J., & Subxanovich, A. A. (2022). THE RISING OF THE INEQUALITY ON THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF PRESCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN.

11. Turapovna, I. S. (2021). Semantics of the lexeme "green". *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 440-448.
12. Машарипов, В. У., Мирвалиева, Н. Р., & Абдуллаев, У. М. (2023). Местный иммунитет и специфическая сенсibilизация к антигенам бактерий у больных тонзиллитом. *Science and Education*, 4(2), 392-400.
13. Сабирова, Н. Э. (2018). ОСОБЕННОСТИ СИМВОЛОВ ОБРЯДОВЫХ ПЕСЕН, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ДРЕВНИМИ КУЛЬТАМИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND EDUCATION* (pp. 73-74).